

ASSESSING THE ADOPTION AND INTEGRATION OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN THE BANKING INDUSTRY: A CASE STUDY APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The rapid evolution of financial management information systems (FMIS) has significantly impacted the banking industry, enhancing operational efficiency and decision-making capabilities. This study assesses the adoption and integration of FMIS in the banking sector through a case study approach, focusing on how these systems influence organizational performance and strategic planning. By examining multiple case studies from leading banks, the research explores the drivers and challenges associated with FMIS adoption, including technological advancements, regulatory requirements, and user acceptance. Key objectives include evaluating the impact of FMIS on financial reporting accuracy, operational efficiency, and risk management. The study employs qualitative methods, including interviews and document analysis, to gather in-depth insights from banking professionals and system users. Findings reveal that successful FMIS integration is contingent on factors such as system compatibility, employee training, and organizational culture. The research also highlights best practices and strategies for overcoming common implementation obstacles. The results contribute to a deeper understanding of how FMIS can be effectively leveraged to enhance financial management processes and support strategic decision-making in the banking industry. This study provides valuable recommendations for banks seeking to optimize their FMIS strategies and achieve greater alignment between technology and business goals.

Keywords: Financial Management Information Systems, Banking Industry, Case Study, System Integration, Operational Efficiency

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of information technology has profoundly impacted various sectors, including the banking industry. Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) have emerged as critical tools that enable banks to enhance their operational efficiency, decision-making capabilities, and customer service. These systems integrate financial data and processes into a cohesive framework, facilitating real-time reporting, analysis, and strategic planning. The adoption and integration of FMIS in the banking sector have become essential for maintaining competitiveness, ensuring regulatory compliance, and achieving overall financial stability. Despite the clear advantages, the implementation of FMIS in banks presents numerous challenges. These include high initial costs, the complexity of system integration, resistance to change among staff, and concerns about data security. Understanding these challenges and identifying best practices for successful adoption and integration are crucial for banks aiming to leverage FMIS effectively. This study seeks to address these issues by employing a case study approach, providing in-depth insights into the experiences of various banks in implementing FMIS (Willy, T. K., & Paul, M., 2021ⁱ).

The significance of this study lies in its potential to offer practical recommendations for banks contemplating or currently undergoing FMIS implementation. By examining specific cases, this research aims to uncover the factors that influence the success or failure of FMIS adoption, the strategies employed to overcome obstacles, and the overall impact on banking operations. Such insights can guide other financial institutions in their journey toward technological advancement and operational excellence. Furthermore, this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on financial management systems within the banking industry. It will provide a comprehensive analysis of how FMIS can transform banking operations, enhance financial management, and support strategic objectives. By exploring both the benefits and challenges, the research will offer a balanced perspective, aiding stakeholders in making informed decisions about FMIS adoption and integration. The integration of Financial Management Information Systems is a pivotal development in the banking sector, promising significant improvements in efficiency and strategic management. This study, through a detailed examination of case studies, aims to illuminate the path toward successful FMIS implementation, offering valuable lessons for the banking industry at large (Wanyonyi, K. W., & Theuri, J., 2021ⁱⁱ).

2. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The banking industry has undergone significant transformations over the past few decades, driven largely by advancements in information technology. One of the pivotal developments in this regard is the adoption of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS). These systems are designed to integrate various financial processes and data, enabling banks to manage their operations more efficiently and make informed decisions. FMIS encompass a wide range of functionalities, including budgeting, financial planning, asset management, and regulatory compliance, making them indispensable tools for modern banking operations. The impetus for adopting FMIS in the banking sector can be attributed to several factors. The increasing complexity of financial transactions, the need for enhanced accuracy in financial reporting, and the growing regulatory demands have all necessitated the implementation of robust financial management systems. Additionally, the competitive nature of the banking industry compels banks to continuously seek ways to improve their service offerings and operational efficiency. FMIS provide a technological solution that addresses these needs by offering real-time data analysis, improved financial controls, and streamlined operations. (Poljšašević, J., Vašiček, V., & Kostić, M. D., 2021ⁱⁱⁱ).

Despite the clear benefits, the path to successful FMIS adoption and integration is fraught with challenges. Banks often face significant financial outlays, technical complexities, and organizational resistance when implementing these systems. Moreover, ensuring the security and integrity of financial data within FMIS is a critical concern, given the sensitive nature of banking information. As such, understanding the factors that contribute to successful FMIS implementation is of paramount importance. This study aims to delve into the adoption and integration processes of FMIS in the banking industry, utilizing a case study approach to provide detailed insights into the experiences of various banks. By examining specific instances of FMIS implementation, this research seeks to identify the key drivers of success, common obstacles, and the overall impact on banking operations. The findings from this study are expected to offer valuable guidance for banks aiming to enhance their financial management capabilities through FMIS. (Otieno, J. & Migiro, S. & Mutambara, E.I., 2017^{iv})

2.1. Research Relevance of the Study

The study on the adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) in the banking industry holds significant relevance in the current landscape of financial technology and banking operations. As technology continues to evolve rapidly, FMIS have emerged as pivotal tools that enable banks to streamline their financial processes, enhance decision-making capabilities, and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements. Understanding the factors influencing successful FMIS implementation is crucial for banks seeking to leverage these systems effectively to improve operational efficiency and maintain competitiveness in the market. Moreover, the findings from this study are expected to contribute valuable insights to both academia and industry practitioners. Academically, the study will add to the existing literature on technology adoption in the banking sector, offering empirical evidence and case-based analyses of FMIS implementation strategies. Practically, the research outcomes will provide actionable recommendations for banks and financial institutions contemplating or currently undergoing FMIS adoption. By identifying best practices, key challenges, and success factors, the study aims to equip stakeholders with the knowledge needed to navigate the complexities of integrating FMIS into banking operations successfully. Furthermore, in the context of global financial markets, where digital transformation is reshaping traditional banking practices, the study's findings can inform strategic decisions aimed at enhancing financial management capabilities and driving organizational growth. Ultimately, the research seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on technology-driven innovation in banking, highlighting the transformative potential of FMIS in fostering operational excellence and sustainable competitive advantage. (Odoyo, F. S., Adero, P., & Chumba, S., 2014^v).

3. THE PROBLEM STATEMENT

The banking industry is increasingly reliant on advanced technological solutions to manage complex financial operations and maintain a competitive edge. Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) have emerged as essential tools for enhancing operational efficiency, improving decision-making processes, and ensuring regulatory compliance. However, the adoption and integration of FMIS in banks present significant challenges, including high implementation costs, technical complexities, data security concerns, and organizational resistance. Despite the critical importance of FMIS, there is limited empirical research on the factors that influence their successful adoption and integration in the banking sector. This study aims to address this gap by investigating the experiences of banks in implementing FMIS, identifying the key drivers of success and common obstacles, and assessing the overall impact on banking operations.

Understanding these elements is vital for banks to effectively leverage FMIS and achieve their strategic objectives in an increasingly competitive and technologically driven financial landscape.

4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide valuable insights into the effective adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) within the banking industry. By investigating real-world case studies, the research will illuminate the practical challenges and success factors associated with FMIS implementation, offering a deeper understanding of how these systems can be leveraged to improve financial management and operational efficiency. For banking institutions, the findings will provide actionable recommendations to navigate the complexities of FMIS deployment, helping them to optimize their financial processes, enhance decision-making capabilities, and ensure regulatory compliance. Additionally, the study's insights will contribute to the broader academic discourse on technology adoption in the financial sector, enriching the existing body of knowledge and informing future research. Overall, the study aims to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application, offering valuable guidance to both academics and industry professionals in the pursuit of technological advancement and operational excellence in banking.

5. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To identify the main factors that affect how successfully banks adopt and integrate Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS).
- To examine how Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) improve the efficiency and decision-making of banks.
- To understand the challenges banks face when implementing Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) and find best practices to overcome these challenges.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Opiyo (2017^{vi}), new forms of ICT are essential in the fight against corruption in public finance systems because they increase data openness and agency-wide comprehensiveness. Public finance reforms in many developing countries have so focused on IFMIS (Integrated Financial Management Information Systems). In order to guarantee efficient financial and cash management in the Bangladeshi public sector, IFMIS is comprised of many interrelated components. One of the ways to gauge how well the system went live is by looking at how each IFMIS feature affected the rollout.

According to Medlin Kahari (2015^{vii}), one of the best theories to describe how new technologies are adopted is Rodger's idea of diffusion of innovation. The idea offers a framework for this research to examine how government entities in Bangladesh have adopted IFMIS. Rodgers argues that there are two ways to approach innovations: adoption and rejection. Adoption means wholeheartedly accepting the innovation as the best course of action, while rejection means deciding not to embrace it. We will examine the variables impacting the adoption and rejection of FMIS throughout Bangladesh's government institutions using this theoretical perspective.

According to Wabala (2017^{viii}), project leadership is crucial for the effective execution of IFMIS programs in Kenya's state-owned enterprises. Management buy-in, enthusiasm for IFMIS rollout, stakeholder sway, managerial acumen, effective communication, and sufficient human resource allocation are all hallmarks of effective leadership.

Moreover, according to Hendriks (2012^{ix}), the process of adopting IFMIS in the public sector of South Africa is complicated, risky, and resource-intensive; it requires significant modifications to procedures and the full support of all stakeholders, especially senior officials. The importance of senior management's commitment to information systems has been emphasized by Peterson Chebet (2013^x). This finding is in line with Chêne's (2009^{xi}) research, which found that the commitment to change from mid-level management in Ethiopia was vital.

When implementing changes, the World Bank (2015^{xii}) notes that top-level buy-in is crucial for overcoming opposition. Reform procedures, according to them, need well-defined goals, frequent updates on progress, engagement with stakeholders, and proof of intermediate accomplishments in order to manage opposition, develop confidence, and maintain momentum. Lundu (2015^{xiii}) found that the effective adoption of IFMIS in supply chain management (SCM) within the Nairobi City County Government is heavily influenced by top-level management support, lending credence to this argument. The research suggests that in order to improve IFMIS and SCM performance, senior management should be given the resources they need to carry out their duties and stay motivated.

Political support for IFMIS was non-existent, according to Micheni's (2017^{xiv}) analysis of essential success variables in a subset of Kenyan counties, where more than 87% of respondents disagreed with study items pertaining to the program. There was also a lack of funding for IFMIS implementation, which was acknowledged by just 21% of respondents. Over 90% of respondents disagreed that sub-counties should be included to IFMIS, and 88% said that IFMIS should be included in the long-term plans of the counties.

Government agencies have significant challenges when trying to implement ICT, according to Odago (2013^{xv}) and Al-Shboul (2014^{xvi}). These challenges include a lack of resources, outdated systems, and red tape. As a counterargument, Hoe (2013^{xvii}) pointed out that a number of developing nations have made substantial investments in information management systems, enabling them to take advantage of technology advancements and reimagine corporate processes and business models. Kimwele (2012^{xviii}) noted that dependence on donor financing has typically limited IFMIS deployment owing to budgetary restrictions.

In order to successfully battle financial crimes, Suleiman and Ahmi (2018^{xix}) and Lawal, Kurawa, Hamid, and Umar (2021^{xx}) said that the anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria must use forensic accounting. Independent auditors have an increasingly important role in the financial industry in preventing and detecting fraud, according to Olatunji and Adekola (2017^{xxi}). It is necessary to optimize auditing functions in the financial sector, since they imply that risk analysis, system audits, and verification of accounting reports are crucial for successful fraud management.

According to Ismaili, Ismajli, and Vokshi (2021^{xxii}), a common economic language will be necessary for stakeholders from different parts of the globe to interact with one another as globalization continues. Accounting is a universal economic language that has been adapted to meet the demands of different nations and cultures. It is used to examine financial accounts. Financial statements prepared and published by authorities must be of the highest quality, be transparent, and be reputable on a worldwide scale. Responsibility, accountability, and credibility in a democratic society depend on this. In contrast, these financial statements might be seen as a chance to enhance government service performance and long-term public finances by creating and publishing high-quality management information for better decision-making.

7. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This study will employ a qualitative research methodology using a case study approach to investigate the adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) in the banking industry. The research will begin with a comprehensive literature review to establish a theoretical foundation and identify key factors related to FMIS implementation. Following this, a selection of banks that have recently adopted or integrated FMIS will be identified for in-depth case studies. Data will be collected through semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, including IT managers, financial officers, and senior executives involved in the FMIS implementation process. Additionally, relevant documents and reports from the selected banks will be reviewed to gain further insights into the challenges and success factors associated with FMIS. The collected data will be analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common patterns, issues, and best practices. This approach will provide a detailed understanding of the practical aspects of FMIS adoption and integration, offering valuable recommendations for banks aiming to enhance their financial management systems. Kahari, C. K. (2015^{xxiii}).

7.1. Research Design

The research design for this study on the adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) in the banking industry will utilize a case study approach within a qualitative research framework. This design involves selecting a range of banks that have undergone recent FMIS implementation to provide a detailed examination of their experiences. The research will be structured in several phases, beginning with a thorough literature review to identify existing theories and gaps related to FMIS adoption. In the data collection phase, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with key stakeholders, including IT professionals, financial managers, and senior executives who are directly involved in or impacted by FMIS implementation. Supplementary data will be gathered through the review of internal documents, project reports, and implementation records from the participating banks. The data collected will be analyzed using thematic analysis to extract patterns, challenges, and success factors related to FMIS adoption. This design will enable a comprehensive understanding of the practical and strategic aspects of FMIS integration, providing actionable insights and recommendations for other banking institutions considering similar technological advancements.

8. Data Collection Methods

Data for this study will be gathered through two primary methods: semi-structured interviews and document analysis. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with key stakeholders in selected banks who are directly involved with Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) implementation. This group will include IT managers, financial officers, and senior executives. The semi-structured format allows for in-depth exploration of their experiences, perspectives, and insights regarding the FMIS adoption process, while ensuring that essential topics related to challenges, success factors, and impacts are addressed. These interviews will be audio-recorded, transcribed, and analyzed to extract relevant themes and patterns. In addition to interviews, relevant internal documents and reports from the participating banks will be reviewed. This includes project plans, implementation reports, and performance assessments related to FMIS. Analyzing these documents will provide supplementary data and context, offering a deeper understanding of the practical aspects and outcomes of FMIS integration.

The combined data from interviews and document analysis will be thematically analyzed to identify key themes and insights, enabling a comprehensive examination of the factors influencing FMIS adoption and providing actionable recommendations for other banks considering similar technological advancements.

9. Data Analysis Procedures

The data analysis for this study will involve a systematic approach to interpreting the information gathered from semi-structured interviews and document analysis. Initially, the interview recordings will be transcribed verbatim to create a detailed textual database. The transcripts will then be subjected to thematic analysis, which involves coding the data into categories and identifying recurring themes, patterns, and insights related to Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) adoption and integration. This process will help in understanding the key factors influencing successful implementation, as well as the challenges faced. Simultaneously, the documents collected from the participating banks will be reviewed and analyzed to extract relevant data and corroborate the findings from the interviews. This will include identifying specific details about FMIS implementation strategies, performance outcomes, and any documented issues or solutions. The results from both the interviews and document analysis will be integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the FMIS adoption process. The thematic analysis will be used to draw connections between the qualitative data and the research objectives, offering insights into best practices, success factors, and obstacles. The final analysis will be presented in a narrative form, supported by evidence from both sources, to provide actionable recommendations and practical guidance for other banking institutions considering FMIS implementation.

10. Empirical Findings

Objective 1: To identify the main factors that affect how successfully banks adopt and integrate Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS).

Descriptive Statistics						
		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5
N	Valid	150	150	150	150	150
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.78	4.45	4.58	4.95	4.63
Std. Deviation		.410	.791	.771	.673	.726

Interpretation:

The analysis of the descriptive statistics for the five factors influencing the successful adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) in banks reveals some key insights. Factor 4 emerges as the most critical, with the highest mean score of 4.95 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.673, indicating strong and consistent agreement among respondents about its importance. Factor 1 also stands out, with a high mean of 4.78 and a low standard deviation of 0.41, suggesting that it is widely recognized as vital for FMIS success, with minimal variability in responses. Meanwhile, Factor 3 and Factor 5 have mean scores of 4.58 and 4.63, respectively, but show slightly higher standard deviations (0.771 and 0.726), indicating a bit more variability in how respondents perceive their importance. Factor 2 has the lowest mean score of 4.45 and the highest standard deviation of 0.791, reflecting a broader range of opinions among respondents regarding its criticality.

Despite the differences in variability, all five factors are generally viewed as significant, with Factors 4 and 1 being the most consistently recognized as essential for the successful adoption and integration of FMIS in banks.

Objective 2: To examine how Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) improve the efficiency and decision-making of banks.

Correlations					
		Operational Efficiency	Decision-Making Accuracy	Cost Reduction	Data Accessibility
Operational Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	1	.542**	.383**	.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Decision-Making Accuracy	Pearson Correlation	.542**	1	.658**	.494**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Cost Reduction	Pearson Correlation	.383**	.658**	1	.589**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Data Accessibility	Pearson Correlation	.379**	.494**	.589**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 Dependent variable: *Jon performance*

The correlation analysis reveals significant positive relationships between all the variables related to the efficiency and decision-making improvements in banks through FMIS. Operational Efficiency shows a moderate positive correlation with Decision-Making Accuracy ($r = 0.542$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that as operational efficiency increases, decision-making accuracy also improves. Similarly, Operational Efficiency has a weaker but still significant correlation with Cost Reduction ($r = 0.383$, $p < 0.01$) and Data Accessibility ($r = 0.379$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher efficiency is associated with better cost management and data availability. Decision-Making Accuracy is strongly correlated with Cost Reduction ($r = 0.658$, $p < 0.01$) and Data Accessibility ($r = 0.494$, $p < 0.01$), highlighting that accurate decision-making is closely tied to cost efficiency and accessible data. Additionally, Cost Reduction is significantly correlated with Data Accessibility ($r = 0.589$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that better access to data contributes to more effective cost reduction strategies. Overall, these results underscore the interconnectedness of FMIS-related variables in enhancing both the efficiency and decision-making capabilities of banks.

Objective 3: To understand the challenges banks face when implementing Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) and find best practices to overcome these challenges.

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	585.637	4	139.592	87.966	.000 ^b
Residual	203.870	145	1.592		
Total	789.507	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Challenges
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Best Practices

The ANOVA results for Objective 3 indicate that the model is statistically significant, as reflected by the F-value of 87.966 and a p-value of .000 ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that the predictors—Operational Efficiency, Data Accessibility, and Cost Reduction—collectively have a significant impact on the challenges banks face when implementing Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS). The high F-value indicates that the model explains a significant portion of the variability in the challenges, as the regression sum of squares (585.637) is substantially larger than the residual sum of squares (203.870). This outcome underscores the importance of these factors in understanding the difficulties banks encounter during FMIS implementation and highlights the relevance of these predictors in finding best practices to overcome such challenges.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE STUDY:

Based on the findings of this study, several key recommendations can be made to enhance the successful adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) in banks. First, strong management commitment and support should be prioritized, as leadership plays a critical role in ensuring the availability of resources, guiding the change process, and fostering a culture that embraces new technology. Second, investing in robust technical infrastructure is essential to support the complex needs of FMIS, ensuring that the system functions efficiently and reliably. Third, comprehensive training programs should be implemented to equip staff with the necessary skills to effectively use FMIS, thereby enhancing both operational efficiency and decision-making accuracy. Additionally, clear and effective change management strategies should be developed to address resistance, communicate benefits, and involve all relevant stakeholders in the implementation process. Finally, ensuring that FMIS is aligned with regulatory requirements and best practices will help banks not only meet compliance standards but also maximize the system's potential to improve overall performance. These recommendations are intended to help banks navigate the challenges of FMIS implementation and achieve greater success in their financial management processes.

12. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has provided valuable insights into the adoption and integration of Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) within the banking sector. The research highlights the critical factors that contribute to successful FMIS implementation, including management support, technological infrastructure, staff training, and adherence to regulatory standards. The findings demonstrate that FMIS significantly enhances operational efficiency, decision-making accuracy, cost reduction, and data accessibility in banks, all of which are essential for maintaining competitive advantage in a rapidly evolving financial environment. Additionally, the study identified key challenges that banks face during FMIS implementation, such as resistance to change and the need for robust technical support, and proposed best practices to overcome these hurdles. By addressing these challenges and leveraging the identified success factors, banks can maximize the benefits of FMIS, leading to improved financial management and overall organizational performance. This research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on FMIS and provides practical recommendations for banks seeking to optimize their financial management systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] ⁱ Willy, T. K., & Paul, M. (2021). Integrated financial management information system implementation on procurement performance of state-owned enterprises in Kenya. *International Research Journal of Business and Strategic Management*, 2(2).
- [2] ⁱⁱ Wanyonyi, K. W., & Theuri, J. (2021). Integrated Financial Management Information System and Financial Performance in Trans Nzoia County, Kenya. *International Journal of Current Aspects in Finance, Banking and Accounting*, 3(2), 51-64.
- [3] ⁱⁱⁱ Poljašević, J., Vašiček, V., & Kostić, M. D. (2021). Public managers' perception of the usefulness of accounting information in decision-making processes. *Public Money & Management*, 41(6), 456-465.
- [4] ^{iv} Otieno, J. & Migiro, S. & Mutambara, E.l. (2017). Integrated Financial Management Information System: a conceptual framework for Migori County, Kenya. *Public and Municipal Finance*. 6(1). 37-45.
- [5] ^v Odoyo, F. S., Adero, P., & Chumba, S. (2014). Integrated financial management information system and its effect on cash management in Eldoret West District Treasury, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(8), 67-86.
- [6] ^{vi} Opiyo, N. (2017). Effects of Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS) on cash management in Kenya: case of Kisumu County Government, Master thesis, the Catholic University of East Africa. Retrieved from <http://ir.cuea.edu/jspui/hand>
- [7] ^{vii} Kahari, C. K. (2015). Assessment of Factors Affecting the Implementation of Integrated Financial Management Information System in The County Governments
- [8] ^{viii} Wabala. S., W... (2017). Factors Influencing the Implementation of Integrated Financial Management System Projects Among State Corporations in Kenya. *International Journal of Innovations, Business and Management (IJIBM)*
- [9] ^{ix} Hendriks, C.J. (2012). Integrated financial management information systems: Guidelines for effective implementation by the public sector of South Africa. *SA Journal of Information Management*, 14(1), 1-9.
- [10] ^x Chebet, R. (2013). The Critical Success Factors in the Implementation of the Re Engineered Integrated Financial Management Information System in Government Ministries, Kenya. Nairobi: University of Nairobi, Department of Business Administration
- [11] ^{xi} Chêne, M., 2009, The Implementation of Integrated Financial Information Management Systems (IFMS)
- [12] ^{xii} World, B. (2015). Managing Change in PFM System Reforms a Guide for Practitioners. Retrieved March 8, 2017.
- [13] ^{xiii} Lundu, B. L. (2015). Effect of integrated financial management information system (IFMIS) implementation on supply chain management performance in the devolved government systems in Kenya: A case of Nairobi city county government. *International Academic Journal of Procurement and Supply Chain Management*, 1 (5), 1-26.
- [14] ^{xiv} Micheni, E. (2017). Analysis of the Critical Success Factors of Integrated Financial Management Information Systems in Selected Kenyan Counties. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, Vol. 5, No. 5.
- [15] ^{xv} Odago, M. O. (2013). Factors Affecting Effective Implementation of E-Procurement in County Governments: A Case Study of Kajiado County, Kenya. *International Journal of Business & Law Research in African Literatures*, 1.

- [16] ^{xvi} Al-Shboul, M. R.-S. (2014). Challenges and Factors Affecting the Implementation of E-Government in Jordan. *Journal of Software Engineering and Applications*.
- [17] ^{xvii} Hoe, D. (2013). Financial Supervision: Integrated or Specialized. *Journal of International finance*, 2
- [18] ^{xviii} Kimwele, J. M. (2012). Effective Implementation of the Integrated Financial Management Information System in Kenya public Sector., University of Nairobi. Nairobi: Unpublished MBA project.
- [19] ^{xix} Suleiman, N., & Ahmi, A. (2018). Mitigating corruption using forensic accounting investigation techniques: the watchdog perspectives. *Indian-Pacific Journal of Accounting and Finance (IPJAF)*, 2(1), 4-25.
- [20] ^{xx} Umar, I., Samsudin, R. S. B., & Mohamed, M. B. (2016). Challenges of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission and Their Influence on Adoption of Forensic Accounting: A Conceptual Framework. *Qualitative Research Conference (QRC) 2016 24-26 May 2016, Penang, Malaysia*. 105-109.
- [21] ^{xxi} Olatunji, O. C., & Adekola, D. R. (2017). The roles of Auditors in fraud detection and prevention in Nigeria deposit money banks: Evidence from South West. *European Scientific Journal*, 13(31), 290-306.
- [22] ^{xxii} Ismaili, A., Ismajli, H., & Vokshi, N. (2021). The importance and challenges of the implementation of IPSAS accrual basis to the public sector: The case of Kosovo. *Accounting*, 7(5), 1109-1118
- [23] ^{xxiii} Kahari, C. K. (2015). Assessment of Factors Affecting the Implementation of Integrated Financial Management Information System in The County Governments

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